

Complex Engineering Problem

Surface Tension Determination in Porous Media Using Lucas–Washburn and Darcy–Washburn Approaches[†]

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Abstract:

Surface tension is important parameter in many physical processes. Measurement of surface tension is highly valuable due to its usage in number of processes ranging from industrial to medical diagnosis. Lucas-Washburn equation is traditionally used to study capillary flow rise and properties can be calculated using it by performing experiment. The horizontal microfluidic channel experiment was performed repeatedly to evaluate the length variation with time. The data is used to calculate the gradient of length square and time graph. To enhance the analysis Darcy's law is integrated and porosity of filter paper is calculated using liquid absorption method. Numerical analysis on data shows that Darcy-Washburn method converges fastly as compared to Lucas-Washburn Method. The surface tension is measured with better accuracy with DW method .

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Introduction

The concept of surface tension provides an idealized yet insightful representation of the interfacial phenomena observed in fluids. Surface tension is an important parameter in fluid flow processes, as many applications and natural phenomena involve liquid mixtures whose properties depend upon surface tension¹.

Molecules within a liquid experience attractive forces from neighboring molecules in all directions. However, at the surface, molecules lack neighboring molecules above them, resulting in a net downward cohesive force². Since cohesive forces (between molecules of the same kind) are

stronger than adhesive forces (between molecules of different kinds), this imbalance of molecular attraction gives rise to the property known as surface tension.

This property depends on both media that share the surface boundary, making surface tension a joint property of two different media. When describing the surface tension of a particular liquid, it typically refers to the interface between the liquid and its own pure vapor at the same temperature³. The surface tension of solids is also quite important as it is useful parameter in adsorption and wettability processes. It is key parameter in many fields affecting size distribution of aerosol produced by nebulizers used in medical industry⁴.

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Studies on measurement of surface tension of aqueous solution are available, but they are restricted to binary solutions and there is scarcity of literature on solution containing more than one solute⁵. It is quite crucial task to measure it for study of surfaces and interfaces. Its dependence on temperature is critical to know due to Marangoni convection. It is actually fluid flow due to surface tension gradient. Metallurgical processes involving free surfaces and fluid phase in which Marangoni convection is leading mass transport process⁶. Solids also have surface stresses but usually they are neglected, but they show central pivotal role in mechanics of soft solids as gels. They differ from fluid as solid surface stresses can be anisotropic and even compressive⁷. Surface tension plays vital role in microfluidic paper based analytical devices (μ PADs). Paper based sensors are used in clinical diagnosis from protein testing to detecting complex DNA⁸.

In packaging industry of production of polymers knowledge of surface tension is required. Recycling of different plastics and their separation and purification is done based on surface tension. To assess the properties of surface coating contact angle and surface tension are determined⁴. Solar stillers are water purification devices that highly depend on evaporation rate. In study⁹ shows that surface tension is major factor that affects the evaporation rates and increasing it enhances the productivity of stillers. Measurement of surface tension of liquids is done using various semiempirical equations or direct measurements. Surfactants are substances which alter the surface properties of liquids. They are composed of lyophilic and lyophobic groups. They move to surface such that lyophilic region lies inside solution and lyophobic group orient itself away from solution¹⁰. The rate of penetration in capillaries was given in 1921 by Washburn that explains the phenomenon of capillary rise¹¹. The ring method known as du Noüy ring method is used for static surface tension measurement. It is measured from force required to pull ring from a liquid¹⁰. It is based on force-time curve for calculation including platinum-iridium ring, sensitive balance through a clamp¹². Drop shape technologies are also widely used for surface tension measurement. Pendant drop method is one of most commonly. In this setup drop formed at end of needle or flat circular holder. The shape of drop affects surface tension measurement, and depends on density difference between fluid & surrounding medium, gravitational acceleration, volume of droplet and diameter of holder. The accuracy of method decreased as droplet become spherical¹³. Another drop based method is sessile drop method in which sessile droplet (droplet on solid surface) is analysed based on its shape to measure surface tension. In study¹⁴ performed image analysis using computational tools to measure surface tension of fluids with accuracy of 10^{-6} mN/m.

Wilhelmy method is plate based method that depends on force required to remove the plate from surface of liquid. A sensitive weight balance is used in it¹⁵. Some techniques are emerging to measure surface tension as AFM (Atomic force microscopy) and holographic optical tweezers⁵. This study focusses on measuring the surface tension of water using Lucas-Washburn equation complemented with Darcy's law of fluid flow in porous media.

Approaches and Methodology

Surface tension of water is measured using Lucas-Washburn equation for capillary rise. Darcy's law of fluid flow in porous medium is combined for enhanced modelling of system. The experimental investigation is done using filter paper in which water flows through it is placed horizontally in a microchannel mold and recorded using camera to capture flow variation with time. Multiple readings are taken for better accuracy. Liquid absorption method was used to find the porosity of filter paper. Image analysis is used to find the flow height variation with time.

Modelling Assumptions

The following assumptions are made in the system to simplify the analysis of the system.

1. The flow in a porous medium is laminar because pores and velocities are small.
2. The permeability is related to porosity and tortuosity by Kozeny-Carman relation.
3. Conditions are isothermal and variation in temperature is negligible so fluid properties like surface tension σ , viscosity μ and density ρ remains constant.
4. The porous medium is isotropic and homogeneous.

Equations

The following equations are used in the analysis

$$\mathbf{q} = - \left(\frac{k}{\mu} \right) \nabla p \quad (\text{Darcy's Law}^{16}) \quad (1)$$

$$k = \frac{\phi r_{\text{eff}}^2}{8 \tau} \quad (\text{Kozeny-Carman Relation}) \quad (2)$$

$$\phi = \frac{V_{\text{void}}}{V_{\text{total}}} \quad (\text{Porosity Relation}) \quad (3)$$

$$\tau = \frac{1.23(1 - \phi)^{4/3}}{\xi^2 \phi} \quad (\text{Tortuosity-Porosity Relation}^{17}) \quad (4)$$

$$\ell^2(t) = \frac{r_{\text{eff}} \sigma \cos \theta}{2 \tau \mu} t \quad (\text{Darcy-Washburn Equation}) \quad (5)$$

where τ is the tortuosity, ϕ is the porosity, q is volume flux, σ is the surface tension, ξ is the shape factor, k is the permeability of the medium, μ is the viscosity of the fluid and θ is the angle of contact.

Experimental Setup

The experiment is performed using grade 41 filter paper. The horizontal microchannel mold was placed horizontally with scale and porous medium is placed in it. Series of experiment were conducted in which flow of fluid through medium was recorded using camera for better accuracy. Image J software was used to analyse the flow height variation with time and was recorded in terms of number of pixels. The scale was defined using the meter rule used in experiment.

Fig. 1 a) Experimental Setup b) Shimadzu Ax200 Analytical Balance

Dropper was used to add distilled water in the mold. For each iteration experiment was conducted for same amount of time. The temperature during experimentation was 20 °C.

Porosity Measurement

Porosity of any porous medium is ratio of void volume to the total volume of medium. It is dimensionless quantity that tells the relative presence of voids in medium. The porosity was measured experimentally using the liquid absorption method. Strip of 60 × 17 mm was used in it. First it was weighed using analytical balance and then it was used as porous medium for fluid flow. It was given ample amount of time for maximum fluid flow and was weighed again. Based on these values of weights and density of water void volume is calculated that is further used to find the porosity by calculating their ratio. The experimental

process yielded the 44% of porosity that was comparable with the literature as calculated in study¹⁸ of 41 grade filter paper as 51.5%. The thickness of filter paper is taken as 215 μm¹⁹.

Angle of Contact

The angle of contact is of great importance in fluids interaction with different phases. It shows the angle that fluid makes when it comes in contact with other states. It is measured from denser phase to less denser phase. Its calculation is required in surface coating materials in accordance with applications. Hydrophobic materials have large obtuse angle of contact while hydrophilic surfaces have acute angle of contact. In study²⁰ angle of contact of different porous medium is calculated. The angle of contact of grade 41 filter paper is 88.09° as calculated by Piyush.

Tortuosity

Tortuosity is the ratio of effective flow path length to straight line distance in flow direction. It is closely related to permeability of fluid, molecular diffusion and electrical conductivity of medium¹⁷. It is calculated based on analytical equation using the porosity relation. It was calculated to be 1.29 that shows in this porous medium circularity of flow as 29%.

Viscosity

Viscosity of fluid is presence of viscous forces in it. It represents the frictional force between each layer of molecules of fluid. It highly affects the flow of fluids in different mediums. Viscosity of water is reference for measuring it for other fluids. In study²¹ shows the precise measurement of viscosity of water at different temperatures. Value of viscosity is taken 1138 μPa·s as calculated by Kestin.

Results and Discussions

This study intended to calculate the surface tension of water using capillary rise method. The Darcy's law of fluid flow in porous medium is used with Lucas-Washburn method for better modelling of system. Lucas-Washburn method uses single capillary, but Darcy's law is statistical average of all the capillaries present in porous medium²². Flow height variation with time is calculated based on experimentation. It shows that slope of height square and time graph is constant showing the linear behaviour. This slope is used in LW equation and Darcy-Washburn equation to calculate the surface tension of water.

This shows that the Darcy's method shows better results than LW method. The standard value of surface tension as calculated in study²³ at 20 °C is 72.8 mN/m.

Symbol	Parameter	Value	Units	Source / Equation	Method	Notes
ϕ	Porosity	0.44	–	$\phi = V_{\text{void}}/V_{\text{total}}$	Measured	Filter paper Grade 41
r_{eff}	Effective pore radius	10 μm	m	Pore size / 2	19	Pore size = 20 μm
τ	Tortuosity	1.29	–	$\tau = \frac{1.23(1-\phi)^{4/3}}{\xi^2 \phi}$	Empirical	ξ = structure factor
k	Permeability	4.263	mm^2	$k = \frac{\phi r_{\text{eff}}^2}{8\tau}$	Kozeny–Carman	Isotropic assumption
μ	Dynamic viscosity of water	1.138 mPa s	$\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$	Standard (25°C)	21	
ρ	Density of water	997	kg/m^3	Standard	21	
g	Gravitational acceleration	9.81	m/s^2	Constant	Physical constant	
θ	Contact angle	88.09°	deg	Grade 41 filter paper	20	Cellulose wetting
σ_{LW}	Surface tension (Lucas–Washburn)	54.9	mN/m	$\ell^2 = \frac{r\sigma \cos \theta}{2\mu} t$	Experimental	Gradient of ℓ^2 vs. t
σ_{DW}	Surface tension (Darcy–Washburn)	70.73	N/m	$\ell^2 = \frac{r_{\text{eff}}\sigma \cos \theta}{2\tau\mu} t$	Experimental	Gradient of ℓ^2 vs. t

Table 1: Calculated physical parameters and material properties used in Darcy–Lucas–Washburn analysis.

Relative error of surface tension calculated using LW method is 24.6% while using the Darcy-Washburn approach it is 2.8%. This shows the accuracy of DW method when applied to porous medium to calculate fundamental fluid property. The Darcy’s approach used although increases the complexity by adding tortoisity and porosity but it models the porous medium in better way. As we plot the surface tension time graph using the data it shows that convergence to standard value of surface tension is faster in Darcy’s method as compared to LW method due to added factors including porosity and taking in account effect of tortoisity increases the convergence of DW method. The plot shows that the surface tension as function of time for both capillary rise measurement techniques. The error percentage of 2.8% shows the efficacy of study and approach used in analysis by using properties of pourous medium to calculate intricate parameters of fluid flow. It can be measued precisely by taking in account porous medium parameters effectively.

Conclusion

This study shows experimental investigation of surface tension using capillary flow method. It studies the different parameters effecting the flow in porous medium and integrate these factors for better modelling of system. The statistically averaged approach was used for capillaries that helped in obtaining the precise results. Porosity and tortoisity was added due to increased complexity due to addition of Darcy’s law of fluid flow. It can be further enhanced by incorporating better regression models and using high resolution image analysis and performing the Scanning electron microscope(SEM) analysis of porous medium will help to characterize pores shape and porosity in well calculated manner also using the controlled environment will further enhance the process.

Figure 2: Lucas-Washburn plot of squared imbibition length (ℓ^2) as a function of time (t)

Figure 3: Surface Tension Convergence Plot DW & LW Method.

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